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EMOTIONAL ENGINEERING THROUGH DICTION AND IMAGERY IN THE LYRICS OF THE SONG "TERJERAT" BY KEY RAN LITERARY PSYCHOLINGUISTIC STUDY

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Abstract: The objectives of this research are 1. How can the language and images contained in the lyrics of the song "Terjerat" by Key Ran influence and stimulate the listener's emotions? 2. Are there differences in emotional interpretation between listeners with different cultural backgrounds regarding the lyrics of the song "Terjerat"? 3. How does the application of linguistic and literary techniques in the lyrics of the song "Terjet" help create a deep atmosphere and support emotional engineering? The method used in this research is a qualitative descriptive method. The approach that researchers will use to analyze the Engineering of Emotions through Language and Imagery in the lyrics of the song "Terjerat" by Key Ran is a textual analysis approach using Harold Bloom's theory (1930) to analyze song lyrics in depth to identify the language and image elements used to convey emotional messages to listeners. Apart from that, researchers used the mental image theory put forward by George Lakoff and Mark Johnson, to analyze the images created by the lyrics that influence the way you hear, understand and feel the song. The subject of this research is the lyrics of the song "Terjerat" by Key Ran. To collect data the technique used is technique. 1. Text analysis 2. Interviews with singers/composers 3. Literature study 4. Listener survey.

The research results show: 1. The language and images contained in the lyrics of the song "Terjerat" can influence and stimulate the listener's emotions based on psychoanalytic engineering analysis, namely: word selection, visual imagery, repetition, grammar and rhythm, language style and metaphor, general themes, and Duality of Emotions 2. Listeners' interpretation after hearing this song is an interpretation based on the meaning of the song's lyrics 3. There is the application of linguistic and literary techniques in the lyrics of the song "Terjerat" which helps create a deep atmosphere and supports emotional engineering as seen from: Listener's emotional understanding, Connection with listeners, Message and meaning of songs, Creativity in the influence of emotions, Psychological Considerations in the Music Industry, Education and Language Arts.

Keywords: Emotional engineering, song lyrics, Psycholinguistics.

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Introduction

Song lyrics often reflect human feelings, experiences and emotions. Through psychological analysis of literature, we can explore the deeper meaning of the lyrics, understand what the songwriter felt, and how these feelings can be understood by listeners. Psycholinguistics is a science that tries to describe the psychological processes that occur when someone utters sentences and understands the sentences they hear when communicating and how humans acquire them (Simanjuntak, 1987:1). Research into Emotional Engineering through Language and Imagery in the Lyrics of the Song "Terjerat" by Key Ran involves a deep understanding of how the lyrics of this song have the power to control and influence the emotions of the listener. Song lyrics are a form of artistic expression that has the potential to create strong emotional connectivity between singer or songwriter with an audience.

The importance of this background lies in the great influence that music and lyrics have on a person's mood and emotions. Song lyrics can be a powerful medium for stimulating feelings such as joy, sadness, passion, nostalgia, and even deep reflection. Therefore, further understanding of how language and imagery in song lyrics can manipulate audience emotions is important.

Methods

The approach that researchers will use to analyze the Engineering of Emotions through Language and Imagery in the lyrics of the song "Terjerat" by Key Ran is a textual analysis approach using Harold Bloom's theory (1930) to analyze song lyrics in depth to identify the language and image elements used to convey emotional messages to listeners. Apart from that, researchers used the mental image theory put forward by George Lakoff and Mark Johnson, to analyze the images created by the lyrics that influence the way we hear, understand and feel the song.

Data Collection Methods (Content Analysis, Case Studies, etc.)

MethodData collection in this research is very important to ensure that the data obtained is relevant, accurate, and in accordance with the research objectives. In the case of research on "Emotional Engineering Through Language and Imagery in the Lyrics of the Song 'Terjerat' by Key Ran," you can choose the following methods to collect data:

a. Text Analysis

Carrying out text analysis of the lyrics of the song "Terjerat" the researcher will analyze the lyrics in depth to identify the language elements and images used to express emotions. Identify language styles, metaphors, analogies, repetition, and the use of key words that have emotional connotations.

b. Interview with Singer/Composer

Conducted an interview with Key Ran (singer/song composer) to provide valuable insight into his intentions behind the song's lyrics. by asking about the inspiration, intent and purpose of using certain language and images in the lyrics.

c. Study of literature

Studying literature related to engineering emotions through language and images can provide a theoretical foundation for identifying relevant theories in emotional psychology, semantics, and literature that can help you in your analysis.

d. Listener Survey

Conduct an online survey of listeners of the song "Terjet" to take views from different points of view. By asking how this song affects their emotions, what parts of the lyrics hit home the most, and what language elements stand out the most.

Results and Discussion

1. Song Lyrics

Entangled
(Key Ran)

Guess the steps

I'm stuck in one direction
Drowning in words
Then it leads to hope
People will talk eye to eye
But we feel what is burning
From the past held tightly
Haunting reluctant to be entangled
Shame on people who don't have anything
I have nothing to lose
And the more I have, the more I will lose
Stunned blankly
Return to direction
Stunned blankly
Stunned blankly
Don't have anything
Drowning question mark
Losing direction
Everything will repeat itself
Take it out of the same hole
Everything repeats itself unintentionally
Get me out of the same hole

2. A brief history of the song "Terjerat" by Key Ran

Of the many contemporary songs circulating, the researcher chose the latest song from Key Ran, which is in the dreamy pop genre, which will only be released in 2023. The musical composition used by Key Ran uses an up-beat which is very pleasant to listen to, but after the researcher examined the lyrics of the song Terjerat, Researchers realized that there were many emotional messages hidden through the figures of speech written by Key Ran. This latest single, produced by Swedish composer Oskar Anderson, made researchers want to identify the analysis of the song's lyrics by providing emotional dimensions in the song lyrics which were identified as emotional engineering through language and images. Researchers will also conduct experiments to measure emotional responses to

data samples, using different groups of listeners who may have different emotional backgrounds. For example, conducting experiments by presenting songs to groups who have different moods before listening to the song.

3. How can the language and images contained in the lyrics of the song "Terjerat" by Key Ran influence and stimulate the listener's emotions?

Engineering analysis Psychoanalysis of Key Ran's song "Terjerat" lyrics

a. Word Choice

- Words like "entangled," "sink," "empty," "empty," "lost," and "same hole" convey intense emotional nuance. They create an image of feelings of being trapped, lost, and an endless cycle.

b. Visual Imaging

- The images of being "stuck in one direction" and "drowning in words" can stimulate the listener's visual imagination, conveying a sense of being trapped and immersed in difficulties.

c. Repetition

- The repetition of the phrases "stomped blank" and "everything repeats itself" increases the emotional intensity and highlights the persistent theme of cycles.

d. Grammar and Rhythm

- The grammatical structure and rhythm of the lyrics can create a feel of sadness or despair, depending on how the song is sung and arranged.

e. Language Style and Metaphor

- "From the past clutched tightly" is an example of a powerful metaphor, creating a figurative picture of how memories of the past can haunt a person.

f. General Theme

- The themes of "loss," "trapping," and repeating cycles appear to create an intense emotional atmosphere and may make listeners reflect on their personal experiences.

g. Duality of Emotions

- The lyrics also depict the duality of emotions, such as the contrast between "People will talk eye to eye" and "But we feel what's burning." This shows the difference between external perception and internal reality.

The lyrics of the song Terjerat raise the anxiety of being a musician who is repeatedly entangled in the same story, in this case we often find that the comfort zone in this case can be anything. When faced with a comfort zone, we often find it difficult to get out of that comfort zone. This song tells the story of the emotions and falls that the author repeatedly goes through. The use of diction that immediately enters one's world often results in an identity crisis when we are repeatedly in the same zone. This song invites listeners who are trapped in their zone to return to their direction. Because after all, the existentialism in this song quite closely conveys the message of getting out of the hole or telling the same story over and over again. In the end, the researcher drew conclusions in the following chapter for further explanation.

4. How do listeners with different cultural backgrounds differ in emotional interpretation of song lyrics (Terjet)

Listener interpretation classification table

Listener Survey				
<i>What do you think after</i>	<i>What is the author's feeling</i>	<i>What influences your feelings</i>	<i>Which part of the lyrics most touchingly/prominently describes the feelings</i>	<i>Are there similarities in emotional</i>

	<i>listening to this song?</i>	<i>(emotional) contained in the lyrics of this song?</i>	<i>(emotional) when listening to this song?</i>	<i>(emotional) in the lyrics of this song?</i>	<i>interpretation between you and the songs you listen to?</i>
1	This song describes how someone is trapped in the past	The author's feelings are complicated and have lost direction due to being entangled in the past	influenced my feelings after hearing this song, namely that I was reminded not to get lost and not to be without direction	The most touching or most prominent thing is in the last part where QT is reminded not to get lost without direction	There is an emotional interpretation where this song has similarities to something I've played before
2	Good, the song lyrics are very deep, and the choice of diction is pleasant to listen to.	Trapped	Remember	"The more you have, the more you will lose"	Yes, because there are emotional similarities between this song and my life in the past
3	Be aware that everything material and worldly in this universe will all have time to disappear	The heart and feelings are drained to get out of a zone that is not like usual, thus sacrificing everything that is temporary	the continuation of life that, on the beat of the seconds it is worth continuing to live	And the more I have, the more I will lose	Steps that are blocked by the magnitude of the dark story of life's past, in the current era of life, entangled and chained but still going well or bad depending on how we solve the problem
4	This song has a deep meaning, such as conveying the feelings we actually experience in response to other people's opinions that do not match reality, how nothingness will come later.	The emotional content is in the form of emotional outbursts expressed in song lyrics	The lyrics have a deep meaning and are the same as current realities that often occur in everyday life.	"The more you have, the more you will lose"	More or less yes, especially in the sentence "people talk with their eyes, but we feel what is burning",

5	The lyrics are so complicated, the arrangement of diction fits every writer's situation	Lyrics that describe the cycle of life just like that. Coming and disappearing, a feeling of loss that is so thickly described by the author "and the more I have, the more I will lose" is the peak of emotion from the creator of these lyrics	These lyrics seem to ensnare the listener to get caught up in the author's emotions to feel the same thing	And the more I have, the more I will lose	Songs are part of life, from social reality and then expressed in song lyrics. And the longer we live, of course the more reality we experience, from these lyrics, the feeling of loss is a common thing faced by everyone and especially our habit of always being stuck in one direction and drowning in words.
6	The song Terjerat has lyrics that are difficult to understand. After listening several times, I finally understand what the song "Terjerat" means	The emotional feeling of the creator of possibilities is like someone who wants to continue a journey in life but is confused and afraid, perhaps due to past, environmental & family factors which might make us lose the direction we are aiming for.	This song tells about a journey in life that is not smooth, the same as my life which is in the process of achieving the desired goals, but because of family and environmental factors that may not understand the purpose of each child's desire to achieve their goals is considered a negative thing.	I have nothing, I have nothing to lose, the more you have the more you will lose	This song has similarities between me and the song I heard, this song is very relatable to the life I live now where the family factor still considers something I make to be negative, even though the life/activities I lived yesterday to today can reduce stress that I've been holding onto all this time
7	cool, poetic and deep lyrics and the	Trapped	Reflecting on the past	The more you have, the more you will lose"	Yes, because there are emotional similarities

	right rhythm of the song				between this song and my life in the past.
8	Cool even though the lyrics are complicated but with the right diction	With the lyrics "And the more I have, the more I will lose" depicts boredom where even though the more you have, the more you lose.	Feeling bored with the same cycle of life, and a feeling of loss that will continue to exist	And the more I have, the more I will lose	Yes

5. How the Application of Linguistic and Literary Techniques in the Lyrics of the Song "Terjerat" helps create a deep atmosphere and supports emotional engineering

a. Listener's Emotional Understanding

This research can help in understanding how word choice, metaphor, and language style in lyrics can influence listeners' emotions. This can be useful in musical and performing arts contexts where emotional expression is essential.

b. Connection with Listeners

Knowing the psycholinguistic elements that create emotional depth in lyrics can help artists or songwriters build better connections with listeners. When lyrics can reflect or permeate common emotional experiences, songs are more likely to generate resonance and identification from listeners.

c. Song Message and Meaning

Analysis can help in exploring the message and meaning that the songwriter wants to convey. Further understanding of language use and lyric structure can provide insight into the song's artistic and narrative purpose.

d. Creativity under the Influence of Emotions

For artists, this analysis can provide inspiration to create more emotionally powerful works of art. Understanding the way words and phrases can evoke emotion can enrich creativity in lyric writing.

e. Psychological Considerations in the Music Industry

In the music industry, psycholinguistic understanding of literature can be an important consideration in designing songs that can attract listeners' attention and emotions. This can influence music production decisions and marketing strategies.

f. Arts and Language Education

Lyric analysis like this can be used in arts or language education contexts to teach students about the power of words, the use of metaphor, and how to convey emotion through linguistic expression.

Discussion

From the results of research conducted on the lyrics of the song "Terjerat" by Key Ran, terjerat conveys the author's emotions about the anxiety felt by the writer and singer about life conflicts that repeatedly occur in the life that should be, like the life that everyone dreams of avoiding conflict. inner self to live a good life following the teachings of each religion adhered to. Song lyrics are a person's expression about something they have seen, heard and felt. Likewise, the song "Terjerat" is a song with a message of anxiety and unrest in the heart of the writer and singer which can be seen from the choice of diction. Songs, like poetry, are literary works written by poets to express what the

poet feels. Each lyric has a deep meaning so it is translated using Leonard B. Meyer's theory. Music and song lyrics have a very important role in conveying emotions to listeners. The combination of musical elements and lyrics is able to create a deep emotional experience and influence the listener's feelings and perceptions. The song "Terjerat" brings the listener in and feels the author's emotions expressed in diction which gives a real depiction of life in general where everyone must have felt the same thing as described in the lyrics of the song "Terjerat". The emotional engineering that can be found in the lyrics of the song "Terjerat" by Key Ran is the use of the author's diction and imagination which is written and becomes a beautiful work that is worthy of being heard or enjoyed so that listeners or lovers of the song "Terjerat" are taken in and feel the content of the song, the feelings and emotions that the author expresses in the lyrics, it can be said that listeners can receive and enjoy this work well, even though the listener's mood and emotions are different from the song they hear. However, the strong imagination of the writer and poet resulted in the diction and emotion of this song being acceptable and able to manipulate the listeners' emotions.

How can the language and images contained in the lyrics of the song "Terjerat" by Key Ran influence and stimulate the listener's emotions?

Engineering analysis Psychoanalysis of Key Ran's song "Terjerat" lyrics

1. Word Choice

- Words like "entangled," "sink," "empty," "empty," "lost," and "same hole" convey intense emotional nuance. They create an image of feelings of being trapped, lost, and an endless cycle.

Based on the analysis, the researcher can describe the choice of words in these lyrics using the word "Terjerat" which can be interpreted as entangled, which can be a figurative type so that the use of entangled may not be in its true meaning, entangled is defined as an association with being bound, deceived or trapped. The use of the word entangled means something that brings the writer or listener to their imagination to interpret the lyrics.

"Drowning" is a meaning that describes a person's condition of being unable to do anything because the situation they are facing is beyond their limits. The general use of the word drowning can mean someone who has fallen into a situation that needs help.

"Ends" The general meaning of the word ends is end. Another meaning of estuary is the place where the river flows in the sea, lake or other river. The use of this diction in the song lyrics gives an idea of a story that ends in life.

"empty" The use of this diction can be interpreted in general terms. The meaning of empty is a figurative type so that the use of empty may not be in its actual meaning. Empty has a meaning in the class of adjectives or adjectives so empty can modify a noun or pronoun, usually by explaining it or making it more specific. Blank. Quiet. The meaning of emptiness in the lyrics of this song describes someone who is in an empty situation. The author describes a sense of loneliness in these lyrics.

"Lost" The general meaning of the word loss is the loss of something. Another meaning of loss is death. This diction is used as the author's description of something that once existed or something that was once owned but no longer owned.

"same hole" The use of this diction comes from the basic word Lubang (Liang). Someone often experiences problems or stories, even the same story is called the same hole.

2. Visual Imaging

The images of being "stuck in one direction" and "drowning in words" can stimulate the listener's visual imagination, conveying a sense of being trapped and immersed in difficulties.

Based on the researcher's analysis, the description of the diction "Stuck in one direction" is how the author describes the direction of a person's steps. This can be included in the figure of speech (going to an unpleasant place), suffering (difficulty, disgrace, etc.), being deceived, being blocked (from freedom, etc.). This is how the author describes how the author is in a situation where he has a

problem.

"sink in words" sinking means falling in the choice of diction, the author gives a description of how words are things that we must properly understand as a form of belief in what we hear. So in the lyrics of this song the author gives an illustration of errors in accepting and interpreting words until it is interpreted that the author has been immersed in the words.

3. Repetition

The repetition of the phrases "stomped blank" and "everything repeats itself" increases the emotional intensity and highlights the persistent theme of cycles.

Based on the analysis, there is a repetition of the phrase "stopping empty", a situation that is described as being oppressed in a void and finding it difficult to get up from the existing situation, while "everything repeats itself" is described in the same situation and always happens. This phrase provides an illustration of the combination of meanings in diction

4. Grammar and Rhythm

The grammatical structure and rhythm of the lyrics can create a feel of sadness or despair, depending on how the song is sung and arranged.

The researcher's analysis of the use of diction and rhythm in the lyrics of the song "Terjerat" has an ability and combination in the use of diction that is appropriate to the choice of song rhythm to convey the message and meaning to the listener, so that they can feel the content of the diction and the author's heart in the mood depicted. The author can interpret and interpret that as a whole the meaning of the content of the song tends to be in a situation of sadness and despair in undergoing the life process and problems faced.

5. Language Style and Metaphor

"From the past clutched tightly" is an example of a powerful metaphor, creating a figurative picture of how memories of the past can haunt a person.

Based on the researcher's analysis, the "language style" used by the author is a language style that really strengthens the writing of this song, namely the association or parable language style so that the diction used gives imagery so it is related to "Metaphor" which is the language style used to compare physical comparisons, traits, even ideas. Then, the language style and metaphors provide a description of the core problems experienced by the author related to the past.

6. General Theme

The themes of "loss," "trapping," and repeating cycles appear to create an intense emotional atmosphere and may make listeners reflect on their personal experiences.

Based on the researcher's analysis of the theme of this song, it can be concluded that listeners can enter this song directly because it is related to the listener's personal emotional experience, everyone must have felt the same situation. Ever been in a phase of loss and trapped in one thing in any context, so the choice of theme for this song was well received and easy for listeners to understand because it relates to the emotional experience of each listener.

7. Duality of Emotions

The lyrics also depict the duality of emotions, such as the contrast between "People will talk eye to eye" and "But we feel what's burning." This shows the difference between external perception and internal reality.

The researcher's analysis of the duality of emotions referred to above is that each person has a different emotional level. Sometimes there are many negative and even positive responses when people express opinions without seeking clarity or meaning from what they see or hear, and what happens is that negative responses are expressed without looking at the background or personal life of the writer or those who live it. However, behind the negative response there is also a positive response which spontaneously realizes the similarity or connection of what they see and hear. Because of this, the reality is that life has similarities and even experiences that are fundamentally the same as each other.

The lyrics of the song Terjerat raise the anxiety of being a musician who is repeatedly entangled in the same story, in this case we often find that the comfort zone in this case can be

anything. When faced with a comfort zone, we often find it difficult to get out of that comfort zone. This song tells the story of the emotions and falls that the author repeatedly goes through. The use of diction that immediately enters one's world often results in an identity crisis when we are repeatedly in the same zone. This song invites listeners who are trapped in their zone to return to their direction. Because after all, the existentialism in this song quite closely conveys the message of getting out of the hole or telling the same story over and over again. In the end, the researcher drew conclusions in the following chapter for further explanation.

How do listeners with different cultural backgrounds differ in emotional interpretation of song lyrics (Terjet)

Interpretation from listeners is needed to help researchers know the extent to which this research is relevant. So the researcher gives important points to seek opinions as data to the listeners which are made in the following questions:

a. What do you think after listening to this song?

Various interpretations have been given by listeners about this song so that researchers can conclude the results of listeners' interpretations that the song "Terjerat" by Key Ranhas a deep meaning, such as conveying the feelings actually experienced by the author and us as listeners in responding to problems that are not in accordance with reality, how nothingness will come later. The lyrics of this song are very deep, and the choice of diction is pleasant to listen to. This song describes how someone is trapped in the past. Responses from listeners provide good points and assessments about this song in terms of the choice of diction and the meaning conveyed by the author. The response stated that the choice of diction for this song was very complicated, but the meaning of the diction chosen was very deep and in accordance with the reality of existing life.

b. What is the author's feeling (emotional) contained in the lyrics of this song?

Listener's interpretation of the author's feelings (emotions) in the song "Terjerat" With the lyrics "and the more I have, the more I will lose" depicts boredom where even though the more you have, the more you lose. The lyrics just describe the cycle of life. "Coming and disappearing", a feeling of loss that is so strongly described by the author "and "the more I have, the more I will lose" is the peak of the emotions of the creator of these lyrics. The author's feelings are being complicated and losing direction due to being entangled in the past. From the interpretation of several listeners, the author's emotions (feelings) in the lyrics of the song "Terjet" describe the concept of "Lost".

c. What influences your feelings (emotional) when listening to this song?

The lyrics have a deep meaning and are the same as current realities that often occur in everyday life. These lyrics also seem to ensnare the listener to get caught up in the author's emotions to feel the same thing. The same thing affects the feelings of other listeners after hearing this song, they are reminded not to get lost and not to be directionless. So it could be said that the general factor felt by listeners when hearing this song is that the emotional depiction and personal experience of the writer in the song lyrics has the power to attract the listener's emotions.

d. Which part of the lyrics most touchingly/prominently describes the feelings (emotional) in the lyrics of this song?

- *"The more you have, the more you will lose"*

This is the most touching and prominent lyric in the song "Terjet" from the interpretation of all listeners, the choice of diction "The more you have, the more you will lose" provides a depiction and emotion that really touches the listener's emotions. The author's emotional use of this diction is precisely the main point to ensnare the listener and understand what "loss" means, both personally to the author and even to the listener.

The meaning of these lyrics is that many things in life that are owned cannot always be truly and completely owned. Loss is a Limitation, even the answer that gives meaning to this. A life worthy

of being owned by many people does not escape the word "Lost" in any case.

e. Are there similarities in emotional interpretation between you and the songs you listen to?

From the many interpretations of listeners, the things that can be gained to learn about the emotional levels of various people through the lyrics of this song are songs are part of life, from social reality and then expressed in song lyrics. And the longer we live, of course the more reality we experience, from these lyrics, the feeling of loss is common for everyone and especially our habit of always being stuck in one direction and drowning in words. This song has similarities between the listener and the song being heard, this song is very relatable to the life that the listener is living now. So the conclusion from all the interpretations of listeners from different life backgrounds is that this song has the same situation and emotions that both listeners and writers have felt.

How the Application of Linguistic and Literary Techniques in the Lyrics of the Song "Terjet" helps create a deep atmosphere and supports emotional engineering

1. Listener's Emotional Understanding

This research can help in understanding how word choice, metaphor, and language style in lyrics can influence listeners' emotions. This can be useful in musical and performing arts contexts where emotional expression is essential.

2. Connection with Listeners

Knowing the psycholinguistic elements that create emotional depth in lyrics can help artists or songwriters build better connections with listeners. When lyrics can reflect or permeate common emotional experiences, songs are more likely to generate resonance and identification from listeners.

3. Message and Meaning of the Song

Analysis can help in exploring the message and meaning that the songwriter wants to convey. Further understanding of language use and lyric structure can provide insight into the song's artistic and narrative purpose.

4. Creativity in the Influence of Emotions

For artists, this analysis can provide inspiration to create more emotionally powerful works of art. Understanding the way words and phrases can evoke emotion can enrich creativity in lyric writing.

5. Psychological Considerations in the Music Industry

In the music industry, psycholinguistic understanding of literature can be an important consideration in designing songs that can attract listeners' attention and emotions. This can influence music production decisions and marketing strategies.

6. Arts and Language Education

Lyric analysis like this can be used in arts or language education contexts to teach students about the power of words, the use of metaphor, and how to convey emotion through linguistic expression.

Conclusion

Overall, these lyrics paint a complex emotional picture and can stimulate deep reflection in the listener. Psycholinguistic analysis of literature highlights how linguistic elements and language styles can be used to design and convey emotional experiences. Emotional Quality Words: Choose words that have a strong emotional content. For example, words with positive or negative connotations that match the feelings you want to convey.

Affixes and Metaphors: Use affixes or metaphors to give additional dimensions to the meaning of words and create emotional associations.

Dexterity in Delivering Personal Messages: Create lyrics that embrace listeners' personal experiences, making them feel more emotionally connected. These principles can create song lyrics that are more emotionally powerful and can take listeners on a deep emotional journey. It is important to consider

the target emotion you want to achieve and how best to communicate it through words and mental images.

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